

MODERN EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: In today's world, knowledge of English is becoming increasingly important and necessary for successful communication, career growth and personal development. Rapid technological development, globalization and intercultural interaction require us to be able to communicate freely in English.

Keywords: business and international communication, scholarships, international exchange programs, scientific research, technology resources, online courses, informational materials, vocabulary, grammatical constructions.

In this regard, the importance of effective methods of teaching English that can maintain a high level of motivation of students and develop their communication skills is increasing.

Traditional methods of teaching English, although valuable, often limit students' ability to fully master the language. Therefore, today more and more attention is paid to the development and implementation of modern teaching methods that actively involve students in the learning process, encourage them to study independently, and ensure the practical application of knowledge [1].

In this article, we will look at modern methods of teaching English, their advantages over traditional approaches, as well as the challenges and prospects that teachers and students face in the process of implementing new educational practices.

Considering these aspects will allow us to better understand which methods are effective in modern education and what trends will determine the future of English language teaching.

Effective English language teaching is of great importance in today's world for many reasons:

1. Globalization:

English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world and is widely used in business and international communication. Knowledge of English opens doors to international opportunities and provides access to the global labor market.

2. Education and career:

Knowledge of English improves your chances of entering universities abroad, receiving scholarships, participating in international exchange programs and developing a career in international companies.

3. Scientific research:

Many scientific publications and conferences are conducted in English. It is important for

scientists and researchers to know English to exchange knowledge and participate in international research projects [1].

4. Tourism and cultural exchange:

Knowing English makes it easier to travel, communicate with people from different countries, and immerse yourself in world culture through literature, film, and music.

5. Technological innovations:

Many technology resources, online courses, and informational materials are available in English. Effective language skills help you use these resources for personal and professional development.

Overall, effective English language teaching plays a key role in successfully adapting to a rapidly changing world by providing people with the necessary skills for effective communication, learning and professional growth [3].

Traditional methods of teaching English, such as the grammar-translation method, the audio-visual method, the reading and dictation method, have their advantages but also limitations:

1. Grammar-translation method:

➤ Advantages:

Pays attention to grammar and translation, helps to understand the structure of the language.

➤ Restrictions:

Can be boring and not very effective for developing speaking skills, focusing on written rather than spoken language.

2. Audiovisual method:

➤ Advantages:

Using audio and video materials enriches the learning experience and helps to understand pronunciation and context.

➤ Limitations: May be limited in variety of materials, not always effective for all types of learners.

3. Method of learning through reading:

➤ Advantages: Allows you to expand your vocabulary and understand grammatical constructions through context.

➤ Restrictions:

May be difficult for beginning learners due to the complexity of the texts and does not always promote the development of speaking skills.

4. Dictation method:

➤ Benefits: Helps improve spelling and listening skills [2].

➤ Limitations: Can be monotonous and not always effective for developing communication skills.

One of the main limitations of traditional methods is their lack of focus on communication skills and the ability to use language in real situations.

Modern approaches to teaching English, such as the communicative method or the game-based learning method, emphasize practical use of language, interaction and contextual understanding, which promotes more effective learning.

Modern methods of teaching English are aimed at creating a comfortable and interactive environment for learning, active use of the language and development of communication skills.

Some of these methods include:

1. Communicative method:

- ✓ This method focuses on the use of language in real communication situations.
- ✓ The main focus is on developing listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.

2. Method of learning through games:

- ✓ Game elements make learning more fun and effective.
- ✓ Games can help you remember new vocabulary, grammatical constructions and apply them in practice [3].
- ✓ This method promotes the development of creative thinking and the ability to work in a team.

3. Method of teaching through context:

- ✓ Lessons are built around specific real-life situations, which helps students better understand and remember the material.
- ✓ The goal is not only to learn individual words and rules, but also to be able to apply them in context.

4. Method of teaching through technology:

- ✓ The use of interactive applications, online courses, video lessons and audio materials makes learning more accessible and engaging.
- ✓ Technology helps to individualize the learning process and track the progress of each student. These modern methods of teaching English contribute to more effective assimilation of the material, development of English communication skills and increased motivation of students.

There are several reasons why modern methods of teaching English can be more effective and interesting than traditional methods:

1. Active involvement of students:

Modern teaching methods emphasize active student participation in the learning process. This may include discussions, project work, role-playing games, and other interactive techniques that promote better learning [2].

2. Use of technologies:

With the development of technology in education, new opportunities for learning appear. Multimedia resources, online platforms, language learning applications - all this makes the learning process more accessible, exciting and effective.

3. Focus on communication skills:

Modern methods of teaching English are often focused on developing communication skills. This allows students not only to learn grammar and vocabulary, but also to learn to communicate freely in English.

4. Individualization of training:

Modern methods allow a more flexible approach to the needs of each student. The use of

various methods and approaches allows for individualization of training, taking into account the characteristics of each student.

5. Stimulating creative thinking:

Many modern methods of teaching English promote the development of students' creative thinking. This helps them not only to learn the language, but also to apply it in non-standard situations. In general, modern methods of teaching English have great potential for creating an interesting, effective and innovative learning process [1].

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that modern methods of teaching English have great potential for effective and interesting learning. They contribute not only to the acquisition of grammar and vocabulary, but also to the development of communication skills, creative thinking and the ability to use the language in practice. It is important to remember that each student is unique, and the use of various methods allows you to individualize the learning process, making it more effective and exciting. Modern methods of teaching English open up new opportunities for students and teachers, contributing to higher quality and more effective learning.

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